

In 1979, host plants of rice water weevil were reported; 16 were grasses, including *Paspalum distichum*, *B. mutica*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. colona*, *Leptochloa fascicularis*, and *Leptochloa* sp.

Other principal hosts were *Cyperus iria* and *C. esculentus*. Because the irrigation system in Sur del Jibaro uses dams, *Eichhornia paniculata* and *E. crassipes* also are important host plants.

Among the new *L. brevisrostris* host plants that we identified, graminaceous species were more abundant (see table). Both adults and larvae fed on those weeds. □

Accelerative effect of juvenoids and precocene-II on diapause breaking of the larvae of three stem borers (SB)

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Larvae of *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *Chilo auricilius*, and *C. partellus* were collected

by incising the tillers of rice stubble in Dec to Feb 1982-83. Juvenoids hydroprene, methoprene, and precocene-II were applied topically in acetone dilutions at 1µl of the solution/larva. One µl pure acetone was applied in the control treatment. Larvae were reared in individual 5- × 0.5-cm glass tubes plugged with moist cotton and wrapped with black paper. The tubes were put inside a rearing chamber kept at 23 ± 1°C, 70-

80% relative humidity, and an 11-13 h lightdark cycle,

In the control treatment, *S. incertulas*, *C. auricilius*, and *C. partellus* moths developed in Feb-Mar, Feb, and Jun. In treated populations, moths developed earlier (see table), suggesting that these chemicals may accelerate diapause breaking of these stem borer larvae. The intensity of their effect may differ by species. □

Moth appearance from overwintering larvae treated topically with juvenoids and precocene-II, West Bengal, India.

Species	Dose ^a (µg/ individual)	Individuals (no.)		Moth appearance (%), 1982-83									
		Treated	Molted	Dec		Jan		Feb		Mar		Apr-May	Jun
				1-15	16-31	1-15	16-31	1-15	16-29	1-15	16-30	1-15	
<i>S. incertulas</i>	H 10	8	3	67	33								
	H 100	36	12	8	8	83							
	M 10	10	2	100									
	M 100	37	9	67	33								
	C	25	12					17	75	8			
<i>C. auricilius</i>	H 100	40	32		53	47							
	H 200	48	40		100								
	P 50	26	20		50	50							
	P 100	46	23		44	57							
	P 150	46	24		63	38							
	C	25	21				100						
<i>C. partellus</i>	H 100	30	20					60	25	15			
	H 200	35	20		14	86							
	P 50	10	7				71	29					
	C	10	10										100

^aH = hydroprene, M = methoprene, C = control, P = precocene-II.

Life cycle of *Marasmia patnalis*, a leaf folder (LF) of rice in the Philippines

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From Oct to Mar 1984, caterpillars of *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) were observed folding and damaging rice leaves at IRRI. This LF species is widely distributed in Southeast Asia. However, it has escaped attention of rice entomologists because of superficial similarity to the more commonly known LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*.

We studied the life cycle and habits of *M. patnalis* in the greenhouse at 26-34°C

with 70-80% relative humidity. Gravid female moths collected from the field

Life cycle of LF *Marasmia Patnalis* reared on TN1 rice, IRRI, 1984.

Character	Duration ^a (d)		Survival (%)
	Range	Average	
Egg	4-5	4	92.3
Larva	21-25	23	88.0
Prepupa	1-2	1	- ^b
Pupa	7-11	9	74.0
Total development period	33-43	37	
Adult longevity			
Male	4-3	3	
Female	5-7	5	

^an = 60 males and 60 females. ^bNo data.